

Consumer Perception towards Mall Special Reference to Coimbatore

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 2

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Amutha, R., and
N. Bhuvanewari.

“Consumer Perception
towards Mall
Special Reference to
Coimbatore.” *Shanlax
International Journal of
Commerce*, vol. 6,
no. S2, 2018, pp. 56–60.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3243789](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3243789)

Abstract

Marketing is a comprehensive term and it includes all resources and a set of activities necessary to direct and facilitate the goods and services from producer to consumer. A businessman regards marketing as a management function to plan, promote and deliver products to the clients or customers. Human efforts, finance and management constitute the primary sources in marketing. Marketing states with identification of customer wants through products and services. The modern concept of marketing is customer-oriented focuses on earning profit through customer satisfaction. The main objective of this study is to carry on a brief study on customer satisfaction and preference on purchasing behavior of the offer suitable suggestion based on the result of the study. The factors influencing the consumer perception and performance towards mall. The customer awareness level about mall for international. The offer suitable suggestion based on result of the study.

Introduction

The only thing static in human life is “change”. Shopping in India has witnessed a revolution with the change in consumer behavior and the whole format of shopping mall is rocking Indians metros and even the international stages and the smaller towns are buzzing with the small mania. The recent surge in the growth of shopping malls is changing the way of people's shop.

Review of Literature

1. Ileszczyc, Sinha and Timmermans, (2000)[2] formulated and tested a model of mall choice dynamics to measure the effects of consumer demographics on consumer grocery mall choice and switching behavior. A dynamic hazard model was estimated to obtain an understanding of the components influencing consumer purchase timing, mall choice and the competitive dynamics of retail competition. The hazard model was combined with an internal market structure analysis using a generalized factor analytic structure.
2. Ana et al. (2000) [2] conducted an empirical study to find out the factors that influence people of a specific geographic area to shopping centers. They identified three benefits that shoppers receive by going to a specific shopping center, the time it takes the buyer to get to the shopping center, a new factor called first visit.

3. Carpenter and Moore, (2006) [3] identified that product assortment was the single most influential variable affecting the choice of retail format across discount stores, hypermarkets and conventional supermarkets. The customer's perception on the quality of products and assortment are positively related to the patronage of a store image.
4. Eric R. Spangenberg et al., (2004) [4] the researchers elaborated that in the presence of gender-congruent ambient scent, shoppers spent more time in the store bought more items and spent more money on their purchasing and the shopper had intention to visit the store in the future.
5. Kang and James, (2004) [5] found a positive relationship between consumers' perceptions of service quality and their willingness to buy. Service quality perceptions contribute to purchase intentions, also uncovered a significant correlation between service quality and behavioral intentions.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the level of awareness of customers towards the shopping malls in international.
- To find out the customers preferences towards the various aspects of shopping mall.
- To offer suitable suggestion based on the result of the study.

Research Methodology

1. Type of Research

The research was descriptive research.

2. Source of Data

- a) Primary data
- b) Secondary data

Primary data

The primary data are those which are collected for first time and information that a researcher should top way with his interest and types source. The data from field sources may be collected from person who has a find of knowledge about social conditions by following observation interview questionnaire or sampling survey.

Secondary data

Secondary data consist of information that already exist somewhere, which has been collected for specific purpose in this study. The secondary data for this study was collected from various books, websites, journals, magazines and organization brochures.

Survey Method

The related data or information was obtained by personal administration of questionnaire.

Sample size

The sample sizes are 150 respondents by using convenience sampling.

Sampling method

The method for survey was non-probabilistic convenience sampling method analysis with the secondary data. With the data collected from the secondary source we can clearly interoperate that the consumer will prefer to visit malls during offer period. In a time frame of two month there were totally three different offers were executed.

Table 1: Classification of Sample Respondents based on Gender

S.No.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	41	27
2	Female	109	73
	Total	150	100

Source: primary data

Classification of responds based on gender. Gender is an important factor to assess the level of consumers shopping awareness, preferences and perceptions. The sample respondents have been classified according to their gender as male and female. It was found that out of the 900 respondents, 27 percentages of the respondents are male and 73 percentages are female. This study shows that female customers are visiting shopping mall over than mall customers.

Table 2: Classification of Sample Respondents based on Age

S.No.	Age Group	Frequently	Percentage
1	Below 20 years	23	15
2	21-30 years	51	34
3	31-40 years	57	38
4	Above 41-50 years	19	13
	Total	150	100

Source: primary data

The age group of the respondents, 15% of respondents are in the age group of below 20 years, 34% of the respondents are in the age group of 21-30 years, 38% of the respondents are in the age group of 31-40 years, and 13% of the respondents are in age group of above 41-50 years. This study shows that 38% of the respondents are in age group 31-40 years people visiting shopping malls frequently.

Table 3: Classification of Sample Respondents based on Education Qualification

S.No.	Education Qualification	Frequently	Percentage
1	Illiterate	39	26
2	10th	30	20
3	12th	21	14
4	Degree	60	40
	Total	150	100

Source: primary data

Education qualification also determines the level of consumers shopping awareness, preferences and perceptions. Education has a positive impact on social life and the quality of life and vice versa with illiteracy. The educational status of sample respondents has been classified into four categories, i.e., illiterate or not been educated 26% of respondent, 20% of the respondents are educational qualified in 10th, 14% of the respondents are educational qualified in 12th 40% of the respondents are educational qualified in degree. This study shows that majority of the 40% of the respondents are educational qualified in degree.

Table 4: Classification of Sample Respondents based on Marital Status

S.No.	Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
1	Married	112	75
2	unmarried	38	25
	Total	150	100

Source: primary data

The above table shows that out of the total sample of 150 respondents surveyed, 75% of the respondents are married categories. 25% of the respondents are unmarried categories they are majority 75% of the respondents are married in their marital status.

Table 5: Classification of Sample Respondents based on Type of the Family

S.No.	Type of the Family	Frequency	Percentage
1	Joint family	61	51
2	Nuclear family	89	49
	Total	150	100

Source: primary data

To mention about the type of the family of the respondents, it may be 59% of the respondents are under the unclear family, 41% of respondents are under the joint family. It is conclude from most 59% of the respondents are under the unclear family category.

Table 6: Ranking of Shopping Malls-using Kendall Coefficient of Concordance

Shopping Malls	Mean Rank	Rank
Brookfield's plaza	1.68	2
Fun republic mall	1.52	1
Unitea mall	3.07	3
Sri laxmi complex	4.40	4
Cheran towers	4.70	5
Asoka plaza	6.05	6
Singapore plaza	6.59	7

Source: primary data

The respondents were asked to assign the ranks by giving rank 1 to most preferred item and rank 2 to the next most preferred item and likewise the least preferred item by giving rank 7.

Findings

There is no significance difference between reason for purchasing in shopping malls and personal profile of the customers (1. Gender 2. Age 3. Education 4. Occupation 5. Monthly income of the respondents 6. Number of members in the family 7. Earning members in the family 8. Marital status and 9. Type of the family).

There is no significant relationship between perception towards shopping malls and personal profile of the customers (1. gender 2. age 3. education 4. occupation 5. monthly income of the respondents 6. number of members in the family 7. earning members in the family 8. marital status 9. type of the family).

Conclusion

Economic development and the change in consumer culture, shopping malls in India have impressive growth and gradually replaced the traditional department stores and retail outlets. The shopping malls become the major avenue for shoppers. It facilitates variety of shops and create pleasant environment for the shopper, leading the shopper to visit and stay longer. The main affecting factors towards mall have been identified as availability of parking facility, quality and variety of product, reasonable price, mall ambience, entertainments and discount offers. Availability of international brands and new product is also influences the customers to visit shopping mall.

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